

PRODUCTION OF MODIFIED CARBOXYMETHYLCELLULOSE FROM COTTON CELLULOSE, ITS USE AND BIOLOGICAL IMPORTANCE.

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Abstract: This article is about obtaining modified Na-KMS substance from cotton cellulose.

Key words: Cellulose, Na-KMS, synthesis, modification.

Carboxymethylcellulose (KMS) is one of the most widely produced water-soluble simple ethers of cellulose. While water-soluble KMS obtained in the solid phase remains with its valuable physical and chemical properties, it is environmentally safe in production, causes little damage to the environment, and It is widely used in many industries, including construction, food industry, perfumery, synthetic detergents, paper, mining, metallurgy, oil and gas extraction industries. and depending on the degree of polymerization, it is divided into different grades, which, in turn, determines the fields of use. Periodic continuous, semi-periodic methods of synthesis of KMS (in solid and suspension phase) are known.

The process of synthesizing KMS is an exothermic process, with the release of heat. When alkaline cellulose is reacted with an alkylating reagent (sodium salt of monochloroacetic acid), the temperature gradually increases by itself, and the started reaction reaches its end in the ripening process.

Information on preventing or reducing the oxidative-alkaline destruction that occurs during the synthesis of KMS is available in the literature. Organic substances with different structures and properties were used as antioxidants. Phenol, phenol formaldehyde, phenol lignin resin, hydroquinone, anthronilic acid. and gossypol resin, acrylonitrile, etc. are among them. However, the main

disadvantage of using these substances is their toxicity, and regular work with them harms human health.

In our experiments, in the process of synthesizing KMS from cotton cellulose, starch, modified starch powdery cellulose, wastes of oil-oil enterprises (sabstak) were used as modifiers. Modification is carried out by adding 0.1-0.2% (relative to cellulose) during alkaline treatment, alkaline cellulose digestion and carboxymethylation processes.

To obtain cotton cellulose, cotton lint of type B with dimensions of 5-6 mm is used. Dry and wet cleaned cotton lint is boiled in a 2% solution of caustic alkali, bleached in hydrogen peroxide solution in an alkaline environment, washed and dehydrated. Then the carver is treated with a solution of sodium in water (230-240 g/l) for one hour. The excess alkali is squeezed out of the press. It is reacted with salt in the solid phase. The resulting mass is matured and dried.

During the synthesis of KMS, 2 types of modifications are made.

First, powdered potato starch was treated with a solution of caustic sodium (230-240 g/l) in water (230-240 g/l) under a 1:10 module at 25-30 degrees for 1 hour. In this case, starch is strongly digested in an alkaline solution to form a sticky mass. because it was not possible to squeeze out the excess alkali in it. The excess alkali that was not squeezed out is quenched. Taking into account the possibility of hydrolysis of Na-MXSK, starch is treated with the necessary alkali solution in a mono-apparatus method (up to 2.8-3.0 times the weight) given

In the first method, after cellulose is treated with an alkaline solution, 0.1-0.4% of starch is added to the cellulose and then it is carboxymethylated. After the mass is matured, it is dried and ground. after treatment with alkali solution (required for twice the weight), adding Na-MXSK, it is carboxymethylated at 25-35 degrees for 1 hour, after ripening, it is dried and ground. The process was carried out by applying the alkylating reagent to cellulose in different ratios (1:1.1-1.8 mol).

The obtained KMS composition is a partially fibrous light-yellow powdery mass with a solubility in water of 94-96%, degree of substitution 0.72-0.80, degree of polymerization 580-760. 1% The pH of the solution was 11.1-12.3.

The synthesized modified KMS samples were submitted for physico-chemical and structural analysis. Experiments are being continued to determine the relationship between the type and properties of the initial raw materials - the modification method and the properties of KMS.

Literature

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